

CAPE VERDEAN *TA* IN ITS ROLE AS A PROGRESSIVE ASPECT MARKER

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Abstract: This paper deals with the aspectual properties of the preverbal marker *ta* as used in Cape Verdean Creole (CV). It will be argued that, counter to what is generally held in the literature, CV *ta* marks not only habitual but also progressive aspect, most notably in gerundive complement clauses, but also in periphrastic progressive markers found throughout the CV dialect cluster. An added aim is to show that, as a progressive marker, CV *ta* behaves remarkably similar to its Papiamentu (PA) cognate *ta*, whose status as a general imperfective marker ([+habitual, +progressive]) is widely recognized. This way, Maurer's (2009) claim that the aspect markers CV *ta* and PA *ta* are qualitatively different is proven to be invalid.

Keywords: Cape Verdean Creole, Papiamentu, progressive aspect.

1. Introduction¹

This paper reassesses the aspectual properties of the preverbal marker *ta* as used in Cape Verdean Creole (CV)². It will be argued that, counter to

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² CV is spoken on the Cape Verde Islands, situated off the coast of Senegal. Within the CV dialect cluster, a rough distinction must be made between the varieties of Barlavento and Sotavento. Though the standard non-rural varieties of these two branches are largely mutually intelligible, there are some important differences between them that also concern the TMA system (discussed e.g. in Pereira 2000, Bartens 2000, Veiga 2000, Quint 2000b, Holm & Swolkien 2006). In the present

what is found in the literature, CV *ta* marks not only habitual but also progressive aspect. In addition, it will be demonstrated that, as a progressive aspect marker, CV *ta* functions in ways remarkably similar to its cognate *ta* found in Papiamentu (PA)³. As such, this paper is part of an ongoing research project that is concerned with uncovering the linguistic and historical connections between PA and Upper Guinea Portuguese Creole, which, besides CV, also includes the sister creole spoken in Guinea-Bissau and Casamance (GBC) (cf. Martinus 1996; Quint 2000b; Jacobs 2008, 2009a, 2009b, forthcoming).

The need to reassess the aspectual properties of CV *ta* arises in light of the fact that, in the literature on CV, *ta* is generally categorized as [+habitual] and [–progressive] (e.g. Silva 1985:158; 1990:157; Lang 1993:150; Pereira 2000:32; Bartens 2000:51; Rougé 2004:25; Baptista et al. 2007:56-58; Veiga 2000:199). For PA, on the other hand, it is uncontroversial that *ta* can yield both habitual and progressive readings, depending on the context (e.g. Kouwenberg & Ramos-Michel 2007:310). The superficial impression is thus created that PA *ta* and CV *ta* qualitatively differ in that the first is [+progressive] while the latter is [–progressive].⁴ This assumption is reflected by Maurer (2009b:44), who, in a recent contribution to the debate on the origins of PA, affirms that “[t]he Cape Verdean marker *ta* (...) does not function as a progressive marker, in contrast to Papiamentu”.

The aim of the present paper, then, is to show that this assumption needs revision: the data presented below provide evidence that CV *ta* is in fact fully operative as a preverbal progressive aspect marker and, contrary to Maurer’s affirmation, behaves in ways remarkably similar to PA *ta*. The structure of the paper is as follows: Section 2 gives a brief overview of habitual and progressive marking in main clauses as described traditionally in the literature on CV and PA. Section 3, the central part of this paper, examines the synchronic use of CV *ta* as a progressive marker in progressive complement

paper, data from all varieties of CV will be adduced. However, data from the Santiago variety of CV (SCV, locally known as *Badiu*) will predominate, as this is by far the best described one. Up to date socio-linguistic data on CV can be found online: <http://www.sorosoro.org/en/cape-verdean>

³ Papiamentu is spoken on Aruba, Bonaire and Curaçao (jointly referred to as the ABC Islands), situated off the coast of Venezuela. Dialectal differences are largely restricted to the lexicon and phonology and play no role in this paper. General information on PA can be found online: <http://www.sorosoro.org/en/papiamentu-3>

⁴ In this paper, I am merely concerned with the function of *ta* as a preverbal aspect marker. Note, however, that both in PA and CV, *ta* also has copular and future tense marking functions.

clauses, at all times providing parallel examples from PA. Section 4, then, addresses the complex progressive markers found in CV and puts these forward as additional evidence in favor of a [+progressive] status of CV *ta*. Section 5 offers a brief digression on progressive marking in GBC, the continental sister creole of CV. Finally, Section 6 presents some final remarks and conclusions.

2. Habitual and progressive aspect marking in CV and PA⁵

To express habitual, both CV and PA take recourse to the marker *ta*:⁶

- (1) a. SCV *Tudu algen di kesotu ilha ta papia sanpadjudu*
 All person of that.other island HAB speak sanpadjudu⁷
 ‘All people from the other islands speak *sanpadjudu*’ (Lang 2002:684)
- b. PA *Wan ta kanta tur dia*
 Wan HAB sing every day
 ‘Wan sings every day’ (Kouwenberg & Ramos-Michel 2007:310)

For PA, as noted in the introduction, scholars agree that *ta* encodes not only habitual but can, depending on the context, just as easily encode progressivity. This is conveniently illustrated by the comparison of (1b) and (2). For CV, on the other hand, as pointed out in the introduction, *ta* is traditionally not mentioned in discussions of progressive aspect and sometimes explicitly said to be [–progressive] (e.g. Silva 1985:158; 1990:157; Pereira 2000:32). For the Sotavento varieties of CV, here exemplified by the Santiago dialect (SCV), *sata*, *sta* and *sta ta*⁸ are commonly put forward as progressive

⁵ In the study of creoles (e.g. Holm & Patrick 2007:vii) as well as non-creoles (e.g. Bybee et al. 1994:151), the scope of imperfective aspect are traditionally subdivided into habitual and progressive aspect. I do so also in this paper.

⁶ In fact, this feature quite radically sets CV and PA apart from the Portuguese-based creoles spoken in the Gulf of Guinea, where *ka* marks habitual (e.g. Rougé 2004:28). This is important to note, since various scholars (most notably Maurer 2002, 2005) have speculated about possible genetic ties between PA and the Gulf of Guinea Creoles, which are clearly not supported by this piece of data.

⁷ *Sanpadjudu* is the name used by natives of Santiago to designate both the people and the speech varieties of all other Cape Verde Islands (Lang 2002:684).

⁸ There is no agreement on how these three variants correlate semantically and etymologically. Some see *sta* as a reduction of *sata* (e.g. Lang 2009:167), others rather take *sata* to be a variant of *sta ta* (e.g. Silva 1985:141); yet others analyze *sta ta* as a phonetic variant of *sta* (e.g. Suzuki 1994, in Baptista 2002:93). See Quint (2000a:258-260), Baptista (2002:91-93) and Pratas (2007:63-97) for

markers (3). For the varieties of Barlavento, exemplified in (4) by the São Vicente dialect (SVCV), *ta ta* and *tí ta* are generally provided.

- (2) PA *Wan ta kanta awor-akí*
 Wan PROG sing now.here
 ‘Wan is singing right now’ (Kouwenberg & Ramos-Michel 2007:310)
- (3) SCV *Gósi-li m- sata papia ku Djom*
 right now I PROG speak with Djom
 ‘I am speaking with Djom right now’ (Quint 2005:44)
- (4) SVCV *Bo tio e k tí ta falá*
 your uncle be who PROG talk
 ‘It’s your uncle who’s talking’ (Octavio Fontes, p.c.)

However, speakers of CV not seldom take recourse to *ta* in what seem to be progressive contexts (5a-c):

- (5) a. SVCV *Es ka ta falá ma bo!*
 3pl NEG PRES.PROG speak with 2s
 ‘They are not **talking** to you’
 (example, gloss and translation from Swolkien 2009:2)
- b. SCV *i mi li si⁹ tâ morrê dí fome*
 And I here thus PROG die of hunger
 ‘and I’m here **dying** of hunger / **starving**’ (translation of Port. *eu aqui estou morrendo à fome!* Costa & Duarte 1967[1886]:308, 309)
- c. SNCV *amin ali tâ morrê de fôme*
 I here PROG die of hunger
 ‘I’m here **dying** of hunger / **starving**’ (translation of Port. *eu aqui estou morrendo à fome!* Costa & Duarte 1967[1886]:308, 314)

On the basis of similar examples, Bartens (1996:40, 47), is among the few who explicitly characterized CV *ta* as [+progressive] (cf. Thiele 1991:53, 54; Fanha 1987:304).

Still, however, in the absence of a proper context, examples such as (5a-c) are open to different interpretations and by themselves do not suffice to bolster the claim that CV *ta* is operative as a preverbal progressive aspect marker. Therefore, more robust evidence is desirable.

discussions of these markers, their dialectal distribution, and their possible etymologies.

⁹ SCV *si* < Port. *assim* ‘thus, therefore, still, anyway’ (Nicolas Quint, p.c.).

3. Progressive *ta* + V complement clauses in CV and PA

This evidence is available in the shape of complement clauses of the type *ta* + V in which *ta* is unambiguously [+progressive]. These complements, highly productive in CV and PA, have been referred to as ‘gerundive complements’ or ‘gerundive clauses’ by Kihm (1994:210, for GBC, cf. Section 5) and Kouwenberg & Muysken (1995:213, for PA) respectively. Accordingly, Muysken (2001:404, on PA) speaks of complements in which “preverbal *ta* resembles English *-ing* (...) or Spanish *-ndo*”. The feature is discussed in detail below.¹⁰

In many respects, progressive *ta* + V complements (henceforth *ta*_{prog} + V complements) behave similar to English and Iberian gerundives. For instance, in ways quite similar to English and Iberian gerundives, the *ta*_{prog} + V complements typically, but not exclusively, occur

- as complements of complex predicates of the type [V_{aux} + *ta*_{prog} + V]¹¹:

- (6) a. BCV *el kumesa ta kúme*
 3sbegin PROG eat
 ‘He began **eating** (and went on eating)’
 (example and translation from Meintel 1975:220)
- b. PA *Rosamalia a kumisa ta yorá*
 Rosamalia PRF begin PROG cry
 ‘Rosamalia began **crying**’ (Lenz 1928:128)
- (7) a. FCV *ele bira ta papia sima papagaia*
 heturn PROG talk like parrot
 ‘He started **talking** like a parrot’ (Parsons 1923:27)
- b. PA *el a bira ta hari*
 he PRF turn PROG laugh
 ‘he started **laughing**’ (Martinus 1996:172)

¹⁰ The particularities of progressive *ta* + V complement clauses in PA have been discussed by Kouwenberg & Muysken (1995:213-214), Andersen (1990:73-75), Muysken (2001), and (particularly) Maurer (1988:262-269). For CV, as far as I am aware, such a discussion is missing to date, although some authors have referred to the phenomenon in passing (see further below).

¹¹ Pending further investigation, it seems that, in principle, any infinitive-governing verb can take the AUX position, though it is typical for both PA and CV to find such predicates headed by verbs with meanings close to ‘to start’ or ‘to stop’ as well as by movement verbs and verbs roughly meaning ‘to continue, keep on’.

- (8) a. BCV *El fika ta kuzinha, ta lava ropa*
 He stay PROG cook PROG wash clothes
 ‘He kept **cooking, washing** clothes’
 (example and translation from Baptista 2007:75)

- b. PA *kachó a keda ta hou*
 dog PRF stay PROG bark
 ‘The dog kept on **barking**’ (Allen 2007:239)

- in *accusativus cum infinitivo* constructions, as complements of perception verbs:

- (9) a. SCV *N xinti algen ta pintxa pórtal*
 I feel person PROG push door
 ‘I felt somebody **pushing** the door!’ (Lang 2002:671)

- b. PA *Ela sinti e logá ta sagudí*
 hePRF feel the place PROG shake
 ‘He felt the place **shaking**’ (Maurer 1988:268)

- (10) a. SCV *el obi Manel ta sibia*
 hehear Manel PROG whistle
 ‘e heard Manel **whistling**’ (Lang 2002:511)

- b. PA *el a topa Koma Baka ta kana buska kuminda*
 hePRF encounter Mother Cow PROG walk search food
 ‘He encountered Mother Cow **looking** for food’ (Maurer 1988:264)

- as adjectival complements:

- (11) a. SCV *Anton, (...) ku gentis tudu ta kume (...)*
 Thus with people all PROG eat
 ‘Thus, with everybody **eating** (...)’ (Lang 2002:576)

- b. PA *e plantashi ta yen di hende ta kórta (...) tabaku*
 the plantation be full of people PROG cut tobacco
 ‘The plantation was full of people **cutting** (...) tobacco’ (Maurer 1988:264)

- as adverbial complements:

- (12) a. SCV *El fika la, ta skuta-m.*
 hestay there PROG listen.me
 ‘He stayed there, **listening** to me.’¹²
 (example and translation from Baptista 2002:78)

¹² Note that in (8a,b), *fika/keda* serves as an auxiliary meaning ‘keep on’, while in (12a,b), it is a full verb meaning ‘stay, remain’. An ambiguous reading can be

- b. PA *Nanzi a keda atras ta pensa*
 Nanzi PRF stay behind PROG think
 ‘Nanzi stayed behind **thinking**’ (Maurer 1988:264)
- (13) a. SCV *N sta na kasa ta studa* (Bernardino Tavares, p.c.)
 I be in house PROG study
- b. PA *mi ta na kas ta studia*
 I be in house PROG study
 ‘I am at home **studying**’ (Rigmar Haynes, p.c.)
- (14) a. SCV *e ten tres noti di fiu ta toka unbes*
 hehave three night in a row PROG play music nonstop
 lit. ‘he has three nights in a row **playing** music nonstop’
 ‘Three nights in a row, he has been playing music nonstop’ (Lang 2002:776)
- b. PA *Marcel tin basta ratu ta kome djente*
 Marcel have quite a while PROG eat tooth
 lit. ‘Marcel has quite a while **eating** teeth’
 ‘Marcel has been grinding his teeth for quite a while’ (Maurer 1988:265)

It is interesting to notice that Lang (2002) and Maurer (1988) independently described the stative possessive predicate structure exemplified in (14a) and (14b) for SCV and PA respectively:

- SCV *ten dit[erminadu] témpu (ta/na) fase algun kusa* ‘have an X amount of time doing s.th.’ > ‘be doing something for a certain amount of time’ (Lang 2002:776);
- PA *tin X tempu ta hasi algun kos* lit. ‘have an X amount of time doing s.th.’ > ‘be doing s.th. for an X amount of time’ (Maurer 1988:265; cf. Muller 1989:235).

Note, furthermore, that both in PA and CV, the *ta_{prog}* + V complements can occur in series expressing simultaneity of events. In such cases, there is normally no conjunction linking the different complements (15a,b):

- (15) a. FCV *el ta ficâ na ratrato ta abri odjo ta fitchâ,*
 he IMP stay in picture PROG open eye PROG close
ta abri boca ta fitchâ
 PROG open mouth PROG close
 ‘he appears on the pictures **opening** and **closing** his eyes, **opening** and **closing** his mouth’ (Macedo 1979:205)

avoided by the insertion of locative complements, as in (12a,b); temporal complements would render a continuous (‘keep on’) reading of *fika/keda*.

- b. PA *Tur dia mita tendé-bo, ta pasa ku piská,*
 All day I IMP hear.you PROG pass with fish
ta gríta ríba kaya.
 PROG scream on street
 ‘Everyday I hear you passing by with fish screaming on the street.’ (Lenz 1928:265; cf. examples in Maurer 1988:262, 264)

In some of the examples provided thus far, the presence of *ta_{prog}* appears to be optional, while in others it is obligatory (for PA, Maurer 1988:263-269 provides details). For SCV (and possibly other varieties of CV), moreover, *na* can occasionally replace *ta_{prog}* (Lang 2000:27; 2002:e.g. 557, 580, 675, 717, 776). While these matters are interesting for further research, they need not concern us here: the examples suffice to accomplish the primary aim of this paper, which is to show that *ta* is fully operative as a preverbal progressive marker in CV. It is relevant to add in this respect, that the markers canonically put forward as SCV’s progressive markers (*sata*, *sta* and *sta ta*) cannot take the place of *ta* in *ta_{prog}* + V complements. Doing so would lead to ungrammaticality (cf. Quint 2010:141).

Despite the general tendency to label CV *ta* as [–progressive], a number of specialists have in fact recognized the capacity of CV *ta* to encode progressive aspect in *ta_{prog}* + V complements. Some examples:

- Meintel (1975:220, 220fn) discusses the “the uses of *ta* to express progression”, after having drawn attention to the occurrence of progressive *ta* + V complements in the Brava variety of CV (cf. ex. [4a]);
- With respect to the predicate *bira ta perdi* ‘turn-PROG-disappear’ ‘to start disappearing’, Quint (2010:141) details that, where one would expect the progressive marker *sta* or *sata*, “only the imperfective marker *ta* can be used to express the fact that the action expressed by the verb (*perdi*) is taking place”¹⁵ (cf. Quint 2003:139; 2005:43);
- Using the phrase CV *el sei ta ri* ‘he-leave-PROG-laugh’ ‘he left laughing’ as an example, Almada (1961:123) observes that the Portuguese gerund morphology did not integrate in CV; instead, “it is the construction of the infinitive preceded by *ta* which is used, this rule being more within the spirit of the creole”;
- Pratas (2007:41) provides the *accusativus cum infinitivo* construction *N odja-u ta fuma* ‘I-see-you-PROG-smoke’ ‘I saw you smoking’ accompanied by the following comment: “In embedded

¹⁵ All translations of quotes are mine.

contexts which look like non-finite environments, *ta* is (...) needed, yielding some value of Progressive".¹⁴

4. On the origins of complex progressive markers in CV

With the progressive *ta* + V complements in mind, it is interesting to look at (the origins of) the stock of progressive markers found throughout the CV dialect cluster, such as SCV *sata*, *sta ta*, SVCV *ti ta*, *ta ta*, or the past forms SCV *staba ta*, FCV *stá ta*, BaCV *tá ta*, *taba ta* ~ *tava ta* and *tive ta* ~ *tibe ta*.¹⁵

Though the variation is considerable, all these markers have in common that the second (and truly preverbal) element is, indeed, *ta*. The variation is caused by the first element, which (with the exception of *sa* in *sata*) corresponds to a locative copula (or past/anterior form of a copula) in the respective variety of CV. This is unsurprising, considering that locative copulas are regularly selected as auxiliaries for periphrastic progressives (e.g. Bybee et al. 1994:129-131; Heine & Kuteva 2002:276-282).

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¹⁴ Note that the type of progressive complements discussed here seems to be common across creoles, as has been pointed out by Bickerton (1981:99-104) with particular respect to complements of perception verbs. After discussing this structure in Guyanese Creole, he stated: "Similar structures are found in other English creoles, such as Belize Creole (...); in French creoles, such as Haitian Creole and Guyanais; and in Portuguese creoles like Saotomense" (Bickerton 1981:103). Recently, Maurer (2009a:85, 86), has described the feature under discussion for Principense, the big difference being that the progressive aspect marker is *ta* in PA and CV, but *sa* in Principense: *Ê vika sa gô* he-come-PROG-cry 'He came crying' (Maurer 2009a:86).

¹⁵ The following sources were consulted: Lopes Da Silva (1957:139, 140), Almada (1961:111, 112), Costa & Duarte (1967:273), Morais-Barbosa (1975:138), Cardoso (1990:65, 66); Pereira (2000:33fn); Bartens (2000:51); Veiga (2000:198); Quint (2000a:258-260; 2000b:75, 76), Baptista (2002:91-93), and Pratas (2007:63-97).

In the literature on CV, these complex markers are still commonly characterized or glossed as single units or as the combination of two TMA markers. However, such a characterization does not account for the fact that all the complex progressive markers (again, with the exception of *sata*) are discontinuous: e.g. SCV *El sta senpri ta kume* he-be-always-PROG-eat 'He's always eating' (Baptista 2002:93) or SVCV *Um tava so ta falá* I-be.PST-only-PROG-speak 'I was merely chatting' (Octavio Fontes, p.c.).¹⁶ For instance, an example such as SCV *El sta senpri ta kume* is glossed by Baptista (2002:93) as he-TMA-always-TMA-eat 'He's always eating', which is at odds with the fact that TMA markers tend to occur before verbs rather than adverbs. Clearly, *sta* here functions as a copula / auxiliary rather than as a TMA marker, while *ta* marks progressive aspect on the complement verb.

If the analysis provided above is correct, the complex progressive aspect markers found throughout the CV dialect cluster provide additional synchronic evidence for a [+progressive] status of CV *ta*¹⁷ (cf. Meintel [1975:220] and particularly Pratas [2007:63-65, 87] for similar analyses).

With the discontinuity of the CV complex progressive markers in mind, the comparison of the commonly heard string PA *ta bezig ta + V* (be-busy-PROG + V) 'be busy V-ing' (cf. Joubert 2007:87; van Putte & van Putte-de Windt 2005:62), exemplified in (16a), with an example of discontinuous SNCV *ta ta* (16b) is compelling: in both cases, *ta*₁ serves as copula/auxiliary, while *ta*₂ marks the complement verb for progressive aspect:

- (16) a. PA *e ta bezig ta traha*
 he be busy PROG work
 'He's busy working' (Lang, George, 2000:93)
- b. SNCV *Katfor ta mitid ta ladra*
 dog be occupied PROG bark
 'The dog is busy barking' (Cardoso 1990:65)

4.1. On the origin of SCV *sata*

One of the particles most typically found marking progressive aspect in main clauses in SCV is *sata* (Quint 2000a:240; Rougé 2004:151; Pratas 2007:63;

¹⁶ The discontinuous character of the complex progressive markers has been remarked upon, for instance, by Cardoso (1990:65), Baptista (2002:87, 93) and Baptista, Mello & Suzuki (2007:56).

¹⁷ It is furthermore implied that progressive predicates such as *sta ta + V* 'to be V-ing' should be analyzed on a par with the periphrastic [$V_{\text{aux}} + ta_{\text{prog}} + V$] predicates described in Section 3, such as *fika ta + V* 'to stay, keep on V-ing'.

Lang 2002:670). As noted, unlike most of the complex progressive markers just discussed, such as BaCV *ta ta*, *tí ta* or SCV *sta ta*, the marker *sata* cannot – or, as I argue, no longer – be analyzed as [$V_{aux} + ta_{prog}$]: synchronically, the first element, *sa*¹⁸, only occurs in this very combination, i.e. prefixed to *ta* (e.g. Lang 2002:670), and is thus not found in SCV as a copula verb.

Diachronically, however, *sata* needs not be excluded from the analysis provided above: *sa* still functions as a locative copula in the conservative Casamance variety of GBC, e.g. *sí kása sa na metádi tera* his-house-be-in-middle-of-village ‘his house is in the middle of the village’ (Bal 1985:35), and appears as such in clearly progressive clauses, e.g. *e sá na kôpo kása* he-be-in/at-build-house ‘he is building a house’ (Bal 1985:23).¹⁹ It is thus likely that, in an early stage, *sa* also served as a locative copula in SCV; we can then reconstruct a process in which a frequent use of the periphrasis [$sa_{cop} + ta_{prog} + V$] ‘to be V-ing’ led to the cliticization of sa_{cop} to ta_{prog} and the crystallization of *sata* as a synthetic progressive aspect marker in SCV, while *sa* did not survive as an autonomous copula verb, at least not in Santiago (cf. Rougé 2004:261 for a similar point).²⁰

¹⁸ Scholars do not agree on the etymology of *sa*: though most seem to believe it is a remnant of Port. *estar* (e.g. Lopes Da Silva 1957:139; Bal 1985:23; Baptista 2002:94; Lang 2002:670; Hagemeyer 2007:58fn), others see it as derived from Port. *ser* (Rougé 2004:261); yet others affirm that *sa* represents a fusion of *ser* and *estar* (Lipski 1993:218). The use of *sa* as a locative copula in GBC (Bal 1985:23, 35; Noël Bernard Biagui, p.c.) seems to favor Port. *estar* as the etymon rather than Port. *ser*. Moreover, the fact that, cross-linguistically, locative copulas are particularly suitable for building progressives (Bybee et al. 1994:128-130) again favors Port. *estar* as the etymon of *sa*, at least in its auxiliary function in progressive SCV *sata + V* and GBC *sa na + V*. Telling in this respect is that, in GBC and SCV, the copulas known to derive from Port. *ser* (GBC *sedu / i* and SCV *ser / e*) are not used as an auxiliary in progressive periphrases, while GBC/SCV *sta* (< Port. *estar*) is. .

¹⁹ To my knowledge, the synchronic use of *sa* as a copula in Casamance has only been documented by Bal (1985). Lipski (2002:72), for instance, in a discussion of copulas found throughout the Iberian-based creoles, explicitly speaks of “la ausencia de *sa/sã* en los criollos de Cabo Verde y Guinea-Bissau”. Moreover, although Rougé (2004:261) mentions the existence of *sa* as a copula in Casamance, he suggests that its use is restricted to fixed expressions such as *I sa* ‘that is to say’. The synchronic use of *sa* as locative copula as documented by Bal, however, has been confirmed to me by Noël Bernard Biagui (p.c.), a native speaker of the Casamance variety of GBC. Bernard Biagui (forthcoming) is currently preparing a linguistic grammar of his mother tongue.

²⁰ It should be mentioned that *sa* is used as a portmanteau copula in all varieties of Gulf of Guinea Portuguese Creole (Lipski 2002:66). In addition, many scholars

Note, finally, that the diachronic analysis of *sata* provided above supports the orthographic tendency to separate *sa* from *ta* by a space, as advocated e.g. by Lang (1993:150) and others.

5. Digression: progressive aspect in GBC

It is now interesting to briefly look at the sister creole of CV, Guinea-Bissau and Casamance Creole (GBC), where *ta* is fully operative as a habitual marker, whereas progressive aspect is encoded with *na* (17). This marker is a reduction of the periphrastic marker *sta na*²¹ ‘be in/at’ (Rougé 1994:147), which is attested in older written sources and can still be heard in the speech of elderly people (Rougé 1993:323).²²

- (17) GBC *N na bibi binyu*
 1s PROG drink wine
 ‘I am drinking wine’ (Kihm 1994:93)

Peck (1988:273), however, mentions that “we have found *ta* to have a progressive meaning in some cases”, providing this example:

- (18) GBC *nho parbai ta chora suma minina*
 Mr. Parbai PROG cry like child
 ‘Mr. Parbai was crying like a child’ (Peck 1988:273)

have drawn attention to the occurrence of *sa(r)* as a portmanteau copula verb (i.e. with properties of both *ser* and *estar*) in several 15th-16th century *Língua de Pretu* texts (Lipski 1993:218; Rougé 2004:261) should not be missing in the present context. Lipski (2002) exhaustively documents the attestations of *sa* (and its variants) in 15th-16th century *Língua de Pretu* texts. Although it is tempting to speculate about a possible transfer of *sa* from the *Língua de Pretu* to the Portuguese-based creoles, such a claim is difficult to substantiate. See Lipski (2002) for an interesting discussion of this issue.

²¹ In addition to encoding progressivity, GBC *na* functions as a future marker. Analogue to the development of GBC *na* out of *sta na*, the Haitian French Creole progressive aspect and immediate future marker *ap* results from the erosion of the preposition *après* ‘after’ which in turn was used in the verbal periphrasis *être après à + V* ‘to be V-ing’ (DeGraff 2007:104).

²² Also in SCV, periphrastic *sta na* can be used to mark progressivity and is occasionally reduced to *na*, though without reaching the levels of grammaticalization that *na* has in GBC (Quint 2000a:264-65)

More interestingly, as in CV, GBC *ta* is a preverbal progressive aspect marker in periphrases of the type [$V_{\text{aux}} + ta_{\text{prog}} + V$]:

- (17) GBC *i kumsa ta coora*
 hebegin PROG cry
 ‘He began to cry (and continued crying)’
 (example and translation from Wilson 1962:22)

On the basis of example (17), Wilson (1962) drew the conclusion that “*ta* has progressive meaning when used after an auxiliary verb” (Wilson 1962:22; cf. Boretzky 1983:130), which corresponds to the situation described above for CV *ta*. Kihm (1940:30) confirms this progressive use of *ta*, providing a rather similar example (*mininu kumsa ta cora* child-start-PROG-cry ‘The child began to cry’). It seems, however, that $ta_{\text{prog}} + V$ complements have gradually become rather rare in Guinea-Bissau in favor of $na_{\text{prog}} + V$ complements (Kihm 1994:210, 211). For Casamance, Noël Bernard Biagui (p.c.) reports that periphrases of the type [$V_{\text{aux}} + ta_{\text{prog}} + V$] (e.g. *bida/fika/sinta ta + V* ‘start/stay/sit V-ing’) can still be heard in the speech of elderly people, but that the variant structure with *na* is indeed more frequent nowadays.

6. Final remarks and conclusions

The aim of this paper was to demonstrate that CV *ta* is fully operative as a progressive aspect marker. With this purpose, Section 3 focused in detail on the use of *ta* in $ta_{\text{prog}} + V$ complement clauses. Maurer’s (2009b:44) claim that “[t]he Cape Verdean marker *ta* (...) does not function as a progressive marker, in contrast to Papiamentu” is inconsistent with the data presented in that section. In addition, in Section 4, the rich stock of complex progressive markers found in CV was analyzed as a collection of periphrastic markers of the type [$V_{\text{aux}} + ta_{\text{prog}}$], thus providing additional synchronic evidence of the use of *ta* as progressive marker.²⁵

The synchronic distribution of CV *ta* as a habitual and progressive aspect marker in each of the different CV dialects clearly points towards an early status of CV *ta* as a general imperfective marker, quite like the

²⁵ In this paper, I have not discussed two progressive markers (probably variations of one form) of unascertained etymology found in the speech of elderly speakers of SCV, *áta* and *áita* (Quint 2000a:259; forthcoming; Lang 2002:10). In his forthcoming *Atlas de la langue capverdienne*, Quint reports on the use of these two progressive markers in almost two thirds of the island of Santiago, though mainly in the speech of elderly people. As to the origins of these markers, it is

portmanteau nonpunctual marker once identified by Bickerton (e.g. 1975:6) as a prototypical creole feature. Interestingly, as early as in the late 19th century, Schuchardt (1882:911) had expressed similar thoughts: “Originally, CV *N ta da* means *eu estou dando* ‘I am giving’, a meaning that was blurred to *eu dou* ‘I give’”. In a similar vein, though with respect to GBC, Kihm (1994:92) assumes that, “in some previous stage of the language, *ta* covered the whole field of the imperfective”.

A scenario can thus be unfolded in which CV *ta* started out as a general imperfective marker ([+habitual, +progressive]). Gradually, alternative periphrastic progressives would then come to absorb an important part of progressive aspect in CV. If this scenario is correct, and if we note that CV *ta* also marks future tense (e.g. Baptista 2002:79), an interesting parallel can be drawn with the Dravidian language Kui. In Kui, one single form was once used “for habitual, progressive, and future. With the development of a periphrastic progressive, this older form came to signal just habitual and future” (Bybee et al. 1994:156). The parallel is striking, though with this difference: unlike the Kui marker, CV *ta* has maintained a good portion of its original [+progressive] qualities.

While we may agree upon the diachronic status of CV *ta* as a general imperfective aspect marker, it is merely a matter of taste whether one chooses to maintain this as a synchronic label of CV *ta*: on the one hand, *ta* has largely been ousted from progressive main clauses by other (complex) markers; on the other hand, the [+progressive] nature of *ta* in gerundive complement clauses is a synchronic reality that needs to be addressed in descriptions of TMA in CV.²⁴

The development in CV of alternative, more emphatic progressive aspect markers such as *sata* alongside *ta* is by no means exceptional: it is quite common for a language to develop more than one way of encoding progressive aspect (Bybee et al. 1994:129). In fact, PA provides a case in point: although in PA, *ta* is the only preverbal progressive aspect marker, the Iberian gerund

arguable that they are construed of *ta_{prog}* with the prefixation of a locative adverbial element **a ~ ai*, perhaps derived from the Portuguese locative adverb *ai* ‘there’ (even though **a ~ ai* does not exist separately in SCV). This hypothesis connects well with the general cross-linguistic tendency for progressives to contain “some sense of location” (Bybee et al. 1994:130). Incidentally, *ata* exists also in PA, as a locative adverb: *ata bo kòfi* ‘here is your coffee’ (van Putte & van Putte-de Windt 2005:46).

²⁴ Note, furthermore, that recognizing the status of CV *ta* as a general imperfective “and hence as [+progressive]” is in harmony with this marker’s ability to mark future tense: imperfectives and progressives developing into future tenses is an unmarked phenomenon in creoles (e.g. Parkvall 2000:84; Holm & Patrick 2007:vii) and non-creoles (Dahl & Velupillai 2005; Bybee et al. 1994:276, 277).

morphology (suffix *-ndo*, e.g. *mi ta papiando* ‘I am talking’) is becoming increasingly popular as a way of marking progressive aspect more emphatically (cf. Sanchez 2000; Kouwenberg & Ramos-Michel 2007:310).

As noted in the introduction, this paper is part of a larger project concerned with the origins of PA and the genetic ties with the branch of Upper Guinea Portuguese Creole. The correspondences revealed in this paper add to the growing body of linguistic evidence in favor of the hypothesis that PA, CV and GBC descend from a common ancestor creole (cf. Martinus 1996; Quint 2000b; Jacobs 2008, 2009a, 2009b, forthcoming). Though controversial, this hypothesis is gradually gaining support among linguists (e.g. Hagemeyer 2009:4; Baptista 2009; McWhorter 2010).

Abbreviations

BCV	= Brava variety of CV
CV	= Cape Verdean Creole
FCV	= Fogo variety of CV
GBC	= Guinea-Bissau and Casamance Creole
HAB	= habitual aspect
IMP	= imperfective aspect
PA	= Papiamentu
PRF	= perfective aspect
PROG	= progressive aspect
SCV	= Santiago variety of CV
SNCV	= São Nicolau variety of CV
SVCV	= São Vicente variety of CV

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